

Effect Obesity on High Blood Pressure among the Adult Males of Sri Venkateswara University Students, Tirupati, Chittoor District

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ABSTRACT

Obesity is a significant risk factor in the development of several non-communicable diseases like hypertension and diabetes etc in adults. It is hypothesized that obese subjects may carry high blood pressure phenotype. To test this hypothesis, a cross sectional study was undertaken among the adults of Sri Venkateswara University students and screened 490 subjects who come under inclusion criteria in a random sample design. Information on anthropometry, blood pressure and socioeconomic profiles were procured from the study participants. The mean age was 26.97±9.04 years. The prevalence of hypertension was 9.38%. The prevalence of hypertension elevated among the obese when compared to normal weight subjects (p<0.05). Blood pressure exerted positive correlation with waist hip ratio (p<0.01). Our results affirm that obesity is a significant factor in the predisposition of hypertension.

1. Introduction

Obesity epidemic poses serious public health concern that contributes around 2.6 million deaths worldwide every year (WHO, 2005). Obesity and obesity-related disorders are worldwide concerns in both developing and developed countries. Since many kinds of chronic metabolic diseases are associated with obesity. Due to obesity and related issues among children and adolescent witnessed dramatic increase in the health care costs in the last two decades (Wang G and Dietz WH, 2002). Overweight children have a greater chance of becoming overweight adolescents and obese adults compared to children of normal weight (Sorof et al., 2002). The number of overweight and obese individuals are increases to epidemic proportions who are frequent exposure to energy dense foods and leisure time physical activity (WHO 2002). Overweight and obesity pose a major risk for chronic diseases, which include hypertension, type 2 diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, stroke, musculoskeletal disorders and certain forms of cancer (Tesfaye et al. 2007). At least 2.8 million adults are dying annually due to malnutrition and overweight and obesity are the fifth leading risk for global deaths (WHO, 2010).

Hypertension is a major chronic disorder, which is associated with obesity (Ostchega et al., 2012). In the low and middle income countries hypertension is increasing rapidly forced by diverse health transitions (Mohan et al., 2013). It is clearly indicating that pathophysiological and epidemiological studies finds the presence of essential high blood pressure at a young age is a strong predictor of essential hypertension later in life (McCrindle, 2010 and Chen X and Wang Y, 2008).

Kearney et al. 2005 estimated globally, there are more than one billion overweight adults; at least 300 million of them are obese. It is estimated that 7.1 million deaths are due to high blood pressure, about 13% of the total. Suboptimal blood pressure attributes about 62% of cerebrovascular disease and 49% of ischemic heart diseases. Both hypertension and

obesity are important public health challenges that become epidemic worldwide.

To reduce the prevalence of hypertension among children and adolescents, early identification and treatment of high BP can act as strong pillars for control and prevention of its complications (Singh et al, 2006 & Sunder et al, 2013). Compared with the year 2000, the number of adults with hypertension is predicted to increase by 60% to a total of 1.56 billion by the year 2025 (Kearney et al. 2005). Prospective studies have emphasized that blood pressure levels and the prevalence of hypertension are related to overall and abdominal adiposity (Kotchen et al. 2008). Hence, Obesity and hypertension have become public health issues with rising prevalence globally, associated with increased morbidity and mortality from cardiovascular diseases as well as increased socio-economic costs (Narkiewicz, 2006). Therefore, this study was conducted to find the effect obesity on high blood pressure among the adult males of Sri Venkateswara University students, Tirupati, Chittoor District.

2. Materials and methods

This is a cross sectional study, in which 490 adult males are selected in the age range of 20 to 35+ years in Tirupati town of Chittoor district, Andhra Pradesh. The present study is focusing on blood pressure, anthropometric measurements and social factors using a pretested questionnaire. The study design was approved by the Departmental Ethics Committee. The objectives of the study were explained to all the subjects before obtaining their consent to participate in the study. Each subject was personally interviewed to get the data such as his name, age, place, of birth, health history, smoking and drinking habit, physical activity, level of education and family income. The physical assessment include anthropometric measurements like height (cm), weight (kg), waist circumference (cm) and hip circumference (cm) were recorded

following the Lohman et al., (1988). BMI was determined based on the formula weight in Kg/height in metres square.

The classification of overweight and obesity was defined using the revised criteria for Asian Indians (The Asia Pacific perspective, 2000); underweight: BMI <18.5 Kg/m², normal range: BMI 18.5–22.9 Kg/m², overweight: at risk: BMI 23–24.9 Kg/m², obese I: BMI 25–29.9 Kg/m², obese II: BMI ≥30 Kg/m². Abdominal obesity was diagnosed when waist circumference was ≥102 cm for males as per the National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP, 2002). The arterial blood pressure of each subject was measured twice with a gap of 5 minutes between them by using mercury sphygmomanometer and stethoscope. Before taking the measurement, the subject is asked to sit comfortably. Average systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure were determined from the two measurements. Hypertension - Individuals with systolic blood pressure (SBP) of ≥ 140 and or diastolic pressure (DBP) of ≥ 90 and those who were already under medication were considered as hypertensive (JNC 7, 2003). Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS, 16.0) was used for analysis which includes the computation of descriptive statistics and Pearson's correlation co-efficient.

3. Results and Discussion

Descriptive statistics for the anthropometry and blood pressure in the study population are presented in table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for the anthropometry and blood pressure in the study population

Variables	Male (490)		
	Mean ± S.D		
Age	26.97	±	9.04
Height	167.20	±	6.24
Weight	62.56	±	10.33
BMI	22.39	±	3.57
WC	77.70	±	10.39
HC	90.34	±	7.43
WHR	0.86	±	0.06
SBP	122.95	±	11.86
DBP	71.68	±	9.54

Prevalence of hypertension among the study population is presented in the table 2. The subjects were stratified according to the age groups of 20-24, 25-29 and ≥ 30 and above. The prevalence of hypertension is high in the 20-24 years age group (45.7%) and followed by 30 years and above (43.5%) and 25-29 years age group (10.9%).

Table 2: Prevalence of hypertension among the study population

Age Group	Hypertension				Total	
	Normal		Risk			
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Age Group 20-24	276	62.2%	21	45.7%	297	60.6%
Age Group 25-29	94	21.2%	5	10.9%	99	20.2%
30 Years and Above	74	16.7%	20	43.5%	94	19.2%
Total	444	100.0%	46	100.0%	490	100.0%

Table 3: Distribution of Obesity and hypertension among the study population

Obesity Classification	Hypertension			
	Normal		Risk	
	No.	%	No.	%
Normal (BMI ≤22.99)	275	61.94	18	39.13
Obesity (BMI ≥23.00)	169	38.06	28	60.87
Total (490)	444	1000.0	46	100.0

Table 3 shows the distribution of obesity and hypertension among the study population. The rise in prevalence of hypertension were more drastic in obese (60.87%) compare to normal (39.13%).

Table 4: Descriptive statistics for the anthropometry and blood pressure in the study population age group wise

	Age Group 20-24+				Age Group 25-29				30 Years and Above				F ratio	P value
	N	Mean ± S.D			N	Mean ± S.D			N	Mean ± S.D				
Height	297	167.63	±	6.04	99	167.00	±	6.47	94	166.03	±	6.50	2.45	.088
Weight	297	59.21	±	8.88	99	64.20	±	9.89	94	71.45	±	9.39	65.30	.000
BMI	297	21.07	±	2.98	99	22.99	±	3.10	94	25.93	±	3.16	93.54	.000

WC	297	73.14	±	7.29	99	79.35	±	8.52	94	90.35	±	9.52	167.33	.000
HC	297	87.78	±	6.37	99	91.38	±	6.56	94	97.36	±	6.62	80.24	.000
WHR	297	0.83	±	0.05	99	0.87	±	0.05	94	0.93	±	0.07	113.23	.000
SBP	297	122.25	±	11.30	99	122.17	±	10.51	94	125.97	±	14.34	3.82	.023
DBP	297	69.93	±	8.99	99	71.17	±	7.97	94	77.74	±	10.33	26.69	.000

The descriptive statistics for age, different anthropometric and blood pressure among the males are presented in table 4. As age increases we observed weight in 20-24 age group it is (59.21) and in age group 30 years and above it is observed that there is increased in weight as (71.45). The rise in the mean value for BMI was more drastic at age group 30 years and above is 25.93. And for SBP and DBP the mean values are higher in 30 years above age group is 125.97 and 77.74 respectively. Whereas in the case of WC, HC and WHR the

mean values are increased according to age group. The mean values for the above are 90.35, 97.36 and 0.93 respectively.

Table 5 shows the Pearson's correlation coefficients between, Age, body composition measures and blood pressure among adult males. Age has positive association with anthropometry and blood pressure. The correlation coefficient of SBP and DBP for age varied from 0.134, 0.307 ($p < 0.01$). The indicators of BMI (0.201; 0.262; $p < 0.01$) and WHR 0.144; 0.284 ($p < 0.01$) were positively associated with blood pressure. Height has no positive with blood pressure.

Table 5. Pearson's correlation coefficients between, Age, body composition measures and blood pressure among adult males.

	Age	Height	Weight	BMI	WC	HC	WHR	SBP	DBP
Age		-.103*	.401**	.466**	.610**	.457**	.556**	.134**	.307**
Height	-.103*		.298**	-.163**	.014	.142**	-.124**	.073	-.008
Weight	.401**	.298**		.890**	.811**	.816**	.542**	.230**	.251**
BMI	.466**	-.163**	.890**		.835**	.776**	.624**	.201**	.262**
WC	.610**	.014	.811**	.835**		.853**	.810**	.199**	.318**
HC	.457**	.142**	.816**	.776**	.853**		.390**	.188**	.252**
WHR	.556**	-.124**	.542**	.624**	.810**	.390**		.144**	.284**
SBP	.134**	.073	.230**	.201**	.199**	.188**	.144**		.543**
DBP	.307**	-.008	.251**	.262**	.318**	.252**	.284**	.543**	
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).									
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).									

4. Discussion

The overall objective of the present study is to find the effect obesity on high blood pressure among the adult males. Adult hypertension is an emerging epidemic in India and the complications of hypertension like stroke, retinopathy, and Coronary artery disease (CAD).

Adults with higher body mass index are at risk in developing high blood pressure. Weight and body mass index are showing strong positive correlation with systolic and diastolic blood pressure levels. Several prospective studies exhibited similar association between weight gain and blood pressure (Kumar et al., 2012). The strong underlying association between obesity and elevated blood pressure may corroborate that increasing prevalence of obesity may likely elevates the blood pressure levels as supported by our data (Flynn, 2008). Blood pressure elevation may lead to increased risk of end-organ damage such as ventricular hypertrophy and increased carotid intima-media thickness and risk of hypertension in adulthood (Markus et al., 2010; Miyaki et al., 2013).

The world epidemic of overweight and obesity is well documented and shows no sign of diminishing (WHO, 2012).

However, although rates are unacceptably high, there is recent evidence of a plateau effect in some high-income countries including the US (Ogden et al., 2010), Sweden (Lissner et al., 2011) and England (NOO, 2010). Comparable data from Low and middle income countries are few, but a recent meta-analysis from China reports that the prevalence of overweight and obesity increased from 1.8% in 1981–1985 to 13.1% in 2006–2010, (Yu et al., 2010) and studies from India show increases in obesity from 9.8% to 11.7% during 2006–2009 (Gupta et al., 2012) with no sign of the flattening seen in high-income countries.

The evidence of the effect of obesity on blood pressure is contradictory and, despite strong evidence that BMI levels are positively associated with both systolic and diastolic blood pressure, there is some evidence from high-income countries that hypertension has not increased in parallel with obesity, although this has not been reported in LMICs (Din-Dzietham et al., 2007; Dong et al., 2013). The association between adult obesity and hypertension is likely to have major impact on subsequent adult health, which in turn will have serious economic and health care implications (Sun et al., 2007; Park et al., 2012).

The association between obesity and hypertension has been reported in numerous studies among a variety of ethnic and racial groups, with virtually all studies finding higher blood pressures and/or higher prevalence of hypertension in obese compared with lean (Sorof et al., 2002). Freedman et al., (1999) reported that overweight adults in the Bogalusa Heart Study were 4.5 and 2.4 times as likely to have elevated systolic blood pressure and diastolic blood pressure. Sorof et al., (2002) reported a three times greater prevalence of hypertension in obese compared with non-obese adults.

The link between obesity and hypertension may be mediated in part by sympathetic nervous system (SNS) hyperactivity. This state of hyperactivity may include cardiovascular manifestations such as increased heart rate and blood pressure variability, neurohumeral manifestations such as increased levels of plasma catecholamines, and neural manifestations such as increased peripheral sympathetic nerve traffic. Consistent with the SNS hyperactivity hypothesis, the Bogalusa Heart Study reported that, in a biracial group of children, resting heart rate was positively correlated with blood pressure and subcapsular skinfold thickness (Voors et al., 1982) and a hyperdynamic cardiovascular state was positively associated with several measures of obesity (Jiang et al., 1995).

5. Conclusions

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Obesity in adolescents has raised to significant levels globally with serious public health consequences. Obesity is an independent risk factor for hypertension, therefore efforts should be geared towards promoting healthy eating habits and maintenance of healthy weight through health education from childhood in schools and at home to prevent and control future undesirable cardiovascular risks. As high blood pressure was found to be strongly associated with overweight/ obesity in this study, we recommend screening of blood pressures should be carried out in children and adolescents. Unless this epidemic is contained at a war footing, the implications of this global phenomenon on future generations will be serious. Body mass index is the predominant risk factor in the elevation of adult blood pressure levels. The findings of the study strongly advocate the need to implement interventional measures for preventing adult male high blood pressure. Further research is required to quantify the effect of reducing other risk factors of blood pressure and obesity among adult males in Tirupati town.

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